

**A KINETIC AND SPECTROSCOPIC STUDY OF THE HYGROTHERMAL AGEING OF HIGH
TEMPERATURE POLYSTYRYLPIRIDINE (PSP) MATRIX COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the chemical structure changes of PSP matrix composites which were aged in hygrothermal conditions varying from 0 % to immersion for 40, 70 and 90°C. We also studied the effect of thermal spikes at 150°C and 250°C during hygrothermal ageing, on the diffusion characteristics. We have shown :

1°) An irreversible absorption mechanism characterised by several saturation levels. An hydrolysis reaction on the resin was identified using IR and NMR technics.

2°) A chemical degradation for samples which were cycled at 250°C.

Polystyrylpyridine (PSP) is a high temperature resin developed by ONERA and commercialised by SNPE in France (1) . The resin shows excellent fire resistance, absorbs little water and has a high resistance to chemical attack. It retains its properties during exposure at 250°C for one thousand hours and can withstand 400°C for several hours (2) The resin is post cured for 16 hours at 250°C and compared to other high temperature resins it is easier and cheaper to synthesise. These properties makes PSP an attractive candidate as a matrix material for composites over a wide range of applications.

PSP SYNTHESIS

This resin is obtained from the polycondensation of terephthalic aldehyde with the trimethyl 2, 4, 6 pyridine (or collidine). The prepolymer is synthesised at 175°C with an acid catalyst :

1st stage

These PSP matrix composites however are to be used in various environments which could lead to modifications of its properties.

In order to study these effects the following investigations have been carried out :

- environmental ageing of several PSP composites reinforced with T300B carbon fibres, Hercules HTS fibres and E and R glass fibres with and without post curing have been studied. The water uptake of the composites under the conditions shown in Table 1 was determined.

TABLE 1
Testing conditions

Relative humidity	11 %, 29 %, 56 %, 75 %	100 % immersed
Temperature	70°C	40°C, 70°C, 90°C

Subsequent work concentrated on the post cured carbon fibres reinforced PSP. A spectroscopic analysis was undertaken to identify the chemical interaction between the water molecules and the composites. Infrared spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) of Carbon 13 in the solid were employed on the pure resin as well as on the composite.

This was followed by a kinetic and spectroscopy study of the effects of temperature excursions of 150°C and 250°C during periods of water absorption at 70°C and 100 % RH.

KINETICS STUDY ; RESULTS

Exposure to a humid environment of the carbon fibre reinforced PSP composites initially revealed simple Fickian behaviour (3) leading to the saturation of the composite. This was found to be initially completely reversible.

At this stage of ageing, a drying stage at 100°C allowed the water to be removed and the initial weight regained. This indicated that a simple diffusion process was occurring with the water in the material interacting only with the hydrogen bonds. This was confirmed by infrared analysis using a band range of (4000-2600 cm^{-1}) on dried and aged specimens, as shown by figure 1.

A longer exposure revealed a second saturation level and if the composite was dried during this stage, the original weight was not regained, with about a third of the absorbed water being locked into the composite.

The water was clearly interacting chemically with the resin. This effect was further studied using spectroscopic analysis.

The water up-take studies revealed a degradation of glass fiber reinforced PSP during exposure at 90°C, 100 % RH and during immersion. The composite lost weight during ageing, its mechanical properties were adversely affected and investigation by scanning electron microscopy revealed bare fibres at the surface. (figure 2).

SPECTROSCOPIC ANALYSIS

During the irreversible phase an hydrolysis reaction between the resin and the water could be envisaged. The residual ethylinic double bonds are probable sites of attack particularly as traces of the catalyst left over from the cross-linking stage are detectable in the resin.

1°) Analysis of the Composite

a) Infra red Spectroscopy (2000 - 350 cm^{-1})

The relative intensities of the principal infra red absorpsion peaks have been studied, relating to the carboxyl groups and the saturated and unsaturated aliphatic groups. In order to make comparisons between the different specimens, the absorption peaks have been referred to the absorption peak at 1010 cm^{-1} corresponding to the deformation of the aromatic nucleus of the para substituted benzene $\delta(\text{CH})$ which is inert under the conditions envisaged. The infra red spectra of composite specimens subjected to different periods of ageing have been studied. The results are shown in figure 3.a.

Result

The spectra obtained were unable to reveal any modifications in the intensities of the peaks. This may have been due to a lack of resolution of the equipment used which was estimated as being about 2 %. The amount of water combined with the composite was a maximum of 0.7 % by weight and so below the threshold of detection. In addition the presence of the carbon fibres reduced the intensity of the transmitted beam.

N M R Study

This NMR study was inconclusive as it proved impossible to suppress the interaction between nuclear and electronic spins, as is shown in figure 4.a. Due to this difficulty, it was decided to study the unreinforced resin aged under the same conditions as the composite specimens (100 % r.h. and 70°C).

2°) Analysis of the Resina) Infra-red (200 - 350 cm⁻¹) (Figure 3.b)

Table 2 shows the intensities of the principal absorption peaks for the PSP resin taking as reference the δ (CH) benzene deformation peak.

TABLE 2
Resin infrared results

Peaks studied	PSP Before Ageing	PSP After ageing
ν (CHO) 1635 cm ⁻¹	4,98	6,01
ν (CH = CH) 1630 cm ⁻¹	4,07	4,11
ν (CH ₃) 1415 cm ⁻¹	3,66	3,81
γ (CH = CH) cis 680 cm ⁻¹	1,61	1,43
γ (CH = CH) trans 970 cm ⁻¹	3,47	3,77
γ (C = O)/ ν (CH - CH)	1,21	1,46
ν (CH ₃)/ ν (CH = CH)	0,9	0,92

This I.R. study revealed a slight increase in the aldehyde (CHO) groups and a reduction of the ethylenic groups (-CH = CH-).

b) N M R

Figure 4.b shows the NMR spectra for the PSP resins before and after ageing. The peaks referred to, were A_{CH₃}, A_{pt} of junction, A_O, A_{CHO}, the areas under the peaks representing respectively the methyl groups (ortho and

para the 3 carbons- $\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2-\text{CH} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{array}$ - at a junction point, the 3 quaternary pyridinique carbons and the aldehyde group. The three following quantities have been defined.

x_{CH_3} : percentage of methyl groups (ortho and para) with respect to the number of pyridine rings.

$$x_{\text{CH}_3} = A_{\text{CH}_3} / (A_o / 3)$$

x_{CHO} : percentage of aldehyde groups with respect to the number of pyridine rings

$$x_{\text{CHO}} = A_{\text{CHO}} / (A_o / 3)$$

$x_{\text{junction point}}$: percentage of junction points with respect to the number of pyridine rings.

$$x_{\text{junction point}} = \frac{A_{\text{junction pt.}}}{A_o}$$

Table 3 shows the variation of these values due to ageing :

TABLE 3
NMR resin results

	PSP Before ageing	PSP After ageing
$x(\text{CH}_0)$	16 %	25 %
$x(\text{pt. of junct.})$	39 %	39 %
$x(\text{CH}_3)$	58 %	88%
$x(\text{CH}_0)/x(\text{pt. of junct.})$	0,41 %	0,64 %
$x(\text{CH}_3)/x(\text{pt. of junct.})$	1,48	2,26
$x(\text{CH}_0)/x(\text{CH}_3)$	0,28	0,28

It can be seen that during ageing of the resin the increases in the methyl and aldehyde groups were in the same proportions whilst the junction points remained constant.

The above results obtained by infra red and NMR allow the following mechanisms to be proposed which by hydrolysis produces a depolymerisation of the resin.

This produces the rupture of the residual double ethylene bonds left over after cross linking, the formation of aldehyde and methyl bonds.

EFFECTS OF THERMAL CYCLING ON WATER ABSORPTION KINETICS

Each specimen was exposed for one hour at a high temperature (either 150°C or 250°C) and then placed directly in an environmental chamber at 100 % r.h. and 70°C for fifteen days. The specimens were weighed at the end of each cycle.

The results of thermal cycling to 150°C revealed no effect on the saturation levels when compared to specimens which were not exposed to the higher temperature. However excursions to 250°C produced a degradation after a period of eighteen months resulting in a loss of weight of around 4 %. The infra red analysis revealed a transformation of the resin as shown by modifications of the absorption peaks as shown in figure 5. A full interpretation of these observations is yet to be completed.

Figure 1 . Infra red spectrum of composite in the bande range of (4000-2500 cm^{-1})

a) Kelf oil (Support)

b) Composite aged at 100 % rh, 70°C

c) Composite dried at 20°C d) Composite dried at 100°C.

Figure 2 . Glass fibre composite
a) with no degradation

b) with degradation

Figure 3 . Infra red Spectrum
 a) of the composite b) of the resin

a)

b)

Figure 4 . High resolution solid state NMR of ¹³C
 a) of the composite b) of the resin

Figure 5 . Infra red spectrum of cycled and non-cycled carbon fibres composite.

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